

PIEZOELECTRIC POLYMER TACTILE SENSOR ARRAYS FOR ROBOTICS

David G. Pirolo, Capt, USAF
Air Force Systems Command, Space Division
Los Angeles AFB, CA 90009

Edward S. Kolesar, PhD, Major, USAF
Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT/ENG)
Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433

ABSTRACT

The design and fabrication of six piezoelectric polymer tactile sensor arrays (PPTSAs) for robotics has been accomplished. These PPTSAs were evaluated for piezoelectric activity and tactile sensing. Two of the PPTSAs were thermally poled. Each PPTSA consisted of a planar 5 x 5 arrangement of identical, (3 mm x 3 mm) discrete sensors. The discrete sensors were fabricated from a piezoelectric polymer, polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), and aluminum electrodes. PVDF provided a pressure sensing capability. The sensor's spatial configuration contributes information for discerning an object's shape. The PVDF film was evaluated for two film thicknesses (25 and 40 microns) and for two forms (unmetallized and vendor metallized). Two electrode structure fabrication processes were developed to accommodate the inherent chemical and temperature limitations of the PVDF film.

INTRODUCTION

One of the promising applications in robotic research is their utility for refueling aircraft in hazardous environments (e.g., hostile or toxic). In order to accomplish this task, it is necessary to position the refueling stem near the aircraft's port and to insert the stem without causing mechanical damage. This critical positioning and orientation task may be accomplished with or without assistance, depending upon the sensors and computational capabilities available.

A fundamental step towards solving this problem is to develop tactile sensors that would provide information to the controller when contact is made with an object of interest. Ultimately, the sensors could be arranged in a planar array format and possess dynamic sensitivity levels. This spatial

configuration would yield information for discerning an object's shape. Sensors derived from piezoelectric polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) provide the desired tactile sensing capability.

Recently, a device to accomplish the tactile sensing task has been designed and fabricated. The sensor synthesized is referred to as a piezoelectric polymer tactile sensor array (PPTSA). Figure 1 shows the two PPTSA designs that were investigated. Each of these designs contained a 5 x 5 array of identical, discrete sensor elements (3 mm x 3 mm). The discrete sensors were fabricated from piezoelectric PVDF film and metallized electrodes. The PVDF film was biaxially-oriented (Solvay Technologies Inc., New York, NY 10017).

Piezoelectric PVDF film was chosen for this effort because of its desirable piezoelectric, mechanical, and chemical resistance characteristics. This material surmounts the typical disadvantages inherent with piezoelectric ceramics. Ceramics are brittle and cannot be configured with large surface areas or in complex shapes. On the other hand, PVDF film is flexible, durable, chemical resistant, and large thin sheets can be cut or stamped into nearly any shape. The material is also light-weight and transparent.

PPTSA FABRICATION

The square-pad sensor design required additional fabrication steps compared to the stripe-electrode design. The additional steps involved preparing the printed circuit (PC) board substrate. The electrode array on the PC board substrate was patterned using a Kodak high resolution plate (HRP) image, photosensitive dry film, and a ferric chloride etch. A PC board drill press was used to bore the 4 mil diameter holes in the PC board substrate.

The electrode-patterned PVDF film was realized using two different processing techniques. One processing technique involved using unmetallized PVDF film and the other technique used aluminum-metallized PVDF film. Kodak HRP's were used to transfer electrode patterns to the photosensitive dry film.

Metal evaporation masks and a thermal evaporation deposition system were used to realize the electrode structures on the unmetallized PVDF film. The evaporation masks were constructed from 5-mil thick beryllium-copper stock and patterned using a dry film photolithographic and etching process. An eight-turn, tungsten wire filament coil was used in the deposition system. Coil filaments were selected because they produce the lowest sublimation temperatures. This was a concern because temperatures above 100°C degraded the piezoelectric properties of the PVDF film.

A photosensitive dry film and etching system was established to realize the electrode structures from the aluminum covered PVDF film. The dry film removal process was operated at room temperature to minimize etching of the aluminum electrodes and thermal degradation of the PVDF film. The electrode patterns were etched using a 1:500 mixture of hydrofluoric acid and deionized water.

Thermal Poling

A thermal poling process was used to regenerate or enhance the piezoelectric activity of the PVDF film in the PPTSA's. This process involved increasing the temperature of the PVDF film to 120°C. After the PVDF film reached 120°C, a 1 MV/cm steady-state electric field was applied across the thickness of the PVDF film for a 60 minute duration. Next, the temperature of the film was reduced to 50°C. Finally, to complete the process, the electric field was removed after the temperature of the PVDF film fell below 50°C.

The thermal poling arrangement consisted of a power source, an oven, a digital thermometer, and a poling chamber. The power source (Power Designs, model 3K10B, photomultiplier high-voltage supply) was used to apply the electric field across the thickness of the PVDF film. The oven (Tenney, Inc.) was used for elevating the temperature of the PVDF film. A digital thermometer (Omega, model 175-KCL) was used for monitoring the temperature of the PVDF film.

The chamber was designed to accommodate a high voltage (3KV) and a

high temperature (120°C). The poling chamber provided an apparatus for holding the PPTSA during thermal poling. When the power supply was operating, the chamber's two electrodes supplied the electric field across the thickness of the PVDF film.

PIEZOELECTRIC ACTIVITY EVALUATION

The relative piezoelectric activity of the PVDF film in six PPTSA configurations was measured. Table I summarizes the six configurations evaluated. It was decided these configurations could answer key questions concerning the tactile sensor's design. The questions were:

1. Are the square pad design configurations better than (or worse than) the stripe design?

2. Is a thicker PVDF film better than a thinner film? (Better in this question refers to the piezoelectric activity of the PVDF film.)

3. Does one electrode-structure fabrication process adversely effect the PVDF film more than the other process?

4. How does the thermal poling process affect the PVDF film? Is the piezoelectric activity of the PVDF film improved or degraded? What are the limitations of this process? (One stripe design, PPTSA #2, and one square-pad design, PPTSA #13, were chosen from the six PPTSA's for thermal poling.)

The piezoelectric activity measurement was accomplished to determine the relative magnitude of the piezoelectric response of the PVDF film involved in the different PPTSA configurations. The piezoelectric PVDF film produced a voltage response proportional to an applied pressure. Pressures were produced by applying a load (force) over a fixed area. The response of a center and corner discrete sensor element on each of the PPTSA's tested were measured with six different loads (grams): 100, 200, 500, 700, 1000, and 1500. The set of separate measurements were arithmetically averaged to determine the response for each of the loads relative to a discrete sensor element.

A schematic of the arrangement that was used for measuring the piezoelectric activity of a PPTSA configuration is shown in Figure 2. The loading machine was a modified Tukon Hardness Tester. The indenter on the hardness tester was replaced with a blunt point. The voltage

response was measured using a Keithley Programmable Electrometer (model 617). The data was transferred to a Zenith personal computer (model Z-248) through an IEEE-488 interface and stored on floppy diskettes. The electrometer was operated at its fastest collection rate; one data point every 360 milliseconds.

The arithmetic average and standard deviation for each set of discrete measurements for a given load was computed. A linear least squares analysis was applied to the averages characterizing each discrete sensor. For these curves, the piezoelectric voltage responses were plotted on the y-axis, and the loads were plotted on the x-axis. In theory, piezoelectric activity is linear. Thus, the slope of the least squares lines could be considered a proportionality constant between an applied pressure and an observed voltage response. It also follows that the y-axis intercept is a system offset. Ideally, this system offset should equal zero because the condition of zero loading should not produce a piezoelectric voltage response. The linear least squares curve fit results for the PPTSA configurations are summarized in Figures 3 through 8.

DISCUSSION

An analysis of the data provides answers to the four questions that were posed earlier. The first three questions pertained to comparing the sensor design configurations (stripe and square pad), the PVDF film thickness, and the electrode-structure fabrication processes. The fourth question addressed the effects the thermal poling process had on the sensor design configurations.

The stripe and square-pad design configurations each possessed factors that made them both desirable and undesirable. The stripe design configurations were easier to fabricate, but were also very susceptible to failure. For instance, a broken stripe electrode eliminates five sensors, or 20 percent of the active sensor elements in the array. On the other hand, the wiring interface that would be required to access the 5 x 5 matrix of 25 discrete sensor elements in the square-pad design would be more complicated.

A performance comparison between the two PVDF film thicknesses (25 and 40 microns) revealed that the 40 micron thickness was superior. This result is supported by the linear least-squares analysis. By averaging the slopes for the 25 micron thick film (PPTSAs #2, #6,

and #13) and the 40 micron thick film (PPTSAs #4, 8, and 15) (Figures 3 through 8), it was discovered that the 40 micron thick film produced a larger piezoelectric activity response for a given load. This result was expected, since in theory, a thicker film should produce a larger response.

The two electrode-structure fabrication processes each possessed desirable characteristics. Neither of these processes appeared to significantly influence the piezoelectric activity of the PVDF film. However, during fabrication, it was determined that the evaporation process produced more robust stripe electrodes. The stripe electrodes realized using the photolithographic process were fragile and would fracture with repeated flexure.

It was also obvious from the linear least squares analysis that the thermal poling process did not improve the piezoelectric activity. In fact, the piezoelectric activity for the configurations evaluated was typically degraded (on the average) by over 45 percent. In addition, the thermal poling process exhibited several undesirable effects on the sensor configurations. The poling process caused the limited amount of unrestrained PVDF film to wrinkle. The film wrinkled because the 120°C thermal poling temperature relieved the stresses that were induced in the film during the vendor's mechanical stretching process. Consequently, the piezoelectric activity of the restrained portion of the film could similarly be degraded if the stresses within it were also partially relieved.

Finally, the most undesirable effect happened to the square-pad configuration (PPTSA #13). The electric field (1 MV/cm) burned a hole (approximately 1 millimeter in diameter) through the center of one discrete sensor element. The hole was caused because the film was poled at the breakdown field, or because there was a flaw in the film.

CONCLUSION

This research resulted in the successful design and fabrication of six PPTSAs for robotic applications. While this investigation did not unequivocally reveal that one sensor configuration was superior, the analysis supports the conclusion that the square-pad design configuration is slightly more advantageous because it does not have the problem of electrode fractures. The stripe design configuration does possess one significant advantage compared to the

square-pad design; it is simpler to fabricate.

The 40 micron thick PVDF film was determined to be the better candidate. It was shown to possess a higher piezoelectric activity and superior physical characteristics compared to the 25 micron thickness. The higher piezoelectric activity was expected. The unmetallized 25 micron thick PVDF film had the undesirable characteristic of wrinkling when handled.

The two electrode-structure fabrication processes (evaporation and photolithographic) were shown to impart no adverse effects on the piezoelectric activity of the PVDF film. The fragile stripe electrodes produced by the photolithographic process were the only notable deficiency. However, this deficiency cannot be attributed to the actual fabrication process. It was subsequently discovered that the aluminum film on the surfaces of the metallized PVDF film had numerous processing flaws in it. These flaws directly contributed to electrode fractures.

From the linear least squares plots, it is apparent that the DC response voltages for the different PPTSAs were indeed linear. This linear behavior contributes to the goal of being able to resolve pressure gradients. However, an alternative poling procedure must be developed because of the undesirable effects that were observed. It is obvious from the piezoelectric activity data that the thermal poling process degraded the piezoelectric activity of the PVDF film.

Finally, this study produced four PPTSA configurations which performed significantly better than the others. The four configurations were the square-pad design that used the 40 micron thick PVDF film. Both sensor element spacings (500 and 750 microns) and electrode fabrication processes (evaporation and photolithographic) were represented equally in the fabrication of this set.

TABLE I

The Six PPTSA Configurations Evaluated

PPTSA Designator Number	Electrode Structure Process	PPTSA Design	PVDF Film Thickness (microns)	Element Spacing (microns)
2	E	S	25	750
4	E	S	40	750
6	E	S	25	750
8	E	SP	40	750
13	P	SP	25	500
15	P	SP	40	500

E--Evaporation
P--Photolithographic
S--Stripe
SP--Square Pad

Figure 1. The two PPTSA Designs Evaluated.

Figure 2. Schematic of the Piezoelectric Activity Measurement Arrangement.

Figure 3. Linear Least Squares Curve Fit for the PPTSA #2 Configuration. (Unpoled: center - solid squares, corner - open ovals. The vertical axis represents the sensor's average DC response voltage.)

Figure 4. Linear Least Squares Curve Fit for the PPTSA #4 Configuration. (Center - solid diamonds, corner - open diamonds. The vertical axis represents the sensor's average DC response voltage.)

Figure 5. Linear Least Squares Curve Fit for the PPTSA #6 Configuration. (Center - solid squares, corner - open squares. The vertical axis represents the sensor's average DC response voltage.)

Figure 6. Linear Least Squares Curve Fit for the PPTSA #8 Configuration. (Center - solid diamonds, corner - open diamonds. The vertical axis represents the sensor's average DC response voltage.)

Figure 7. Linear Least Squares Fit for the PPTSA #15 Configuration. (Center - solid ovals, corner - open ovals. The vertical axis represents the sensor's average DC response voltage.)

Figure 8. Linear Least Squares Curve Fit for the PPTSA #13 Configuration. (Unpoled: center - solid triangles, corner - open triangles; poled: center - solid inverted triangles, corner - open inverted triangles. The vertical axis represents the sensor's average DC response voltage.)

